

1 **RNASEH1 gene function.**

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6 R-loops are hybrid DNA/RNA structures found to be present in high number in cells maintaining HPV
7 genomes and whose resolution is controlled by genes including RNASEH1. We studied RNASEH1 gene
8 function by gene expression or silencing in cell culture. We demonstrate here control of interferon
9 signaling (*Mx1*, *Ifit1*, *Oasl*) by Rnaseh1 in the cell. Interferon control by otherwise silencing of Rnaseh1
10 featured, and appeared related to, loss of homeostasis marked by *Fbxo32* induction. We present
11 evidence Rnaseh1 interacted with *Pde4c*, *Gch1* and *Cnga1* in cyclin nucleotide signaling. We
12 demonstrate control of cGAS by Rnaseh1.

13 Citations

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